

NATIONAL CONTEXT

There are several acts which are relevant to gender-based violence (GBV) but none of them specifically address Higher Education Institutions. The forms of GBV included in the Criminal Code are rape, sexual assault of a vulnerable person or a child and sexual assault by abusing the position of power and sexual harassment. The Criminal Code was amended in 2017 to implement the Istanbul Convention and now includes other forms of GBV such as stalking. The Labour Act from 2005 defines harassment and sexual harassment as any unwanted behaviour caused on any grounds¹ that is directed at or violates the dignity of a job seeker, or an employee, which causes fear or creates a hostile, degrading or offensive environment. Sexual harassment is further defined as any verbal, non-verbal or physical behaviour that is directed at or violates the dignity of a job seeker and a full-time employee, which causes fear or creates a hostile, degrading or offensive environment.

In relation to higher education, the Law on Science and Research establishes that the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development should be responsible for setting legal and policy framework, including those related to combatting GBV in universities and research organisations. However, no measures have been adopted or envisaged for adoption yet. The Science Fund is the leading research funding institution in Serbia that has the mandate to make a set of criteria related to combating GBV as a precondition for financial support.

Universities and research institutions have only recently been raising the problem of gender-based violence. This has occurred in response to several publicised cases of sexual harassment and assault. The first ever internal rules and regulations on prevention and protection against sexual harassment and blackmail were adopted in 2014 at the Faculty of Political Science of the University of Belgrade. There is also an informal group of 14 University of Belgrade professors who requested a draft and adoption of a University rulebook on the prohibition of sexual harassment and violence, to inform the public about the process and to organise trainings after its adoption. In her urgent response to the initiative, the Rector confirmed that the University of Belgrade has been working on such a document for a long time and that a draft exists.

¹ Gender, birth, language, race, skin colour, age, pregnancy, health condition, disability, nationality, religion, marital status, family obligations, sexual orientation, political or other beliefs, social origin, property status, membership in political organisations, unions or some other personal characteristics.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The law faculty of the Union University developed a Rulebook against Sexual Harassment and Blackmail.

› **URL:** Rulebook against Sexual Harassment and Blackmail:
<http://pravnofakultet.rs/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Pravilnik-o-zastiti-od-seksualnog-uznemiravanja-i-ucenjivanja-22.03.2019..pdf>

Entry into force: 2019

TRAINING

In order to recognise, prevent, and stop sexual harassment, the dean conducts regular information and training of employees and students to recognise the causes, forms, and consequences of sexual harassment and blackmail. However, it is not indicated how these sessions should be organised or how regularly they should take place.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Teaching about GBV is still relatively undeveloped and exists mainly at the undergraduate level. The University of Belgrade's Faculty for Special Education and Rehabilitation introduced a syllabus on violence against women in 2004 (Nikolić-Ristanović, 2019). A recent analysis of the syllabi (undergraduate, master and doctoral level) of three state universities (Belgrade, Novi Sad and Niš) suggests that the topic of domestic violence is the most common. Other forms of GBV are addressed less often (sexual violence, stalking or trafficking in human beings). Almost all of the courses are optional. Despite slight improvements, violence against women as a subject is still in its early stages of development and future research in this area is necessary.

Violence research in Serbia has a long tradition in the academic community but has focused mainly on domestic and intimate partner violence rather than other forms of GBV. Stable and continuous funding of scholarly research on GBV is lacking. As of April 2021, not a single seminar, campaign or roundtable has been supported by the national research funding institutions or ministries to address GBV in universities and research organisations. Women's organisations remain the primary source of data, knowledge and activism, including GBV in research organisations and universities².

² See Sexual violence at the universities in Serbia: Raising awareness and developing innovative mechanisms of victim support, https://www.vds.rs/Projekat_SeksualnoNasiljeNaUniverzitetimaUSrbijiEng.htm

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: the policy addresses the following **three** forms of GBV:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harrassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harrassment | |

7Ps covered: The policy addresses the following **3Ps**: prevention, prosecution, and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

The policy addresses academic staff, non-academic staff, and students.

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes (number of cases and types of violations).

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

The University of Novi Sad sets a **step-by-step procedure** for reporting and investigating cases of GBV applicable to all.³

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, description of the investigation, responsible persons, outcomes, sanctions.

The faculty is obliged to protect students from sexual harassment or sexual blackmail. There are two procedures aimed at prevention and protection: a consultative procedure and a procedure for stopping sexual harassment and blackmail.

Responsible persons: The consultative procedure includes the appointment by the dean of three persons to provide victims with support and assistance.

Who to contact: Within the consultative procedure, a person who believes that s/he has been exposed to sexual harassment or blackmail can turn to any of the three appointed persons for help and support. This procedure is informal, and no official records are kept. Within the procedure for stopping sexual harassment and blackmail, a person who believes that s/he has suffered sexual harassment and/or sexual blackmail submits a written request to initiate the procedure to stop sexual harassment and blackmail. A written request may also be submitted by an employee who learns of conduct that s/he justifiably believes to be sexual harassment or blackmail, doing so with the consent of the person who is believed to have suffered harassment or blackmail. During the procedure, a victim may choose a person of trust to provide support. A person of trust may be present when a victim of sexual harassment or blackmail is giving any testimony. A written request to initiate this procedure is submitted to the dean of the faculty.

How to report: The request should contain:

- Name and surname of the applicant
- Name and surname of the person(s) stated as the perpetrator of sexual harassment or blackmail
- Date(s) when the alleged sexual harassment or blackmail was committed
- Location
- Description of the incident
- Names of witnesses
- Other relevant information, including evidence
- Signature of the person
- Date of submission of the request

If the request does not contain all the required data, it will be considered incomplete. However, the person to whom the request is submitted can instruct and invite the applicant to complete the request himself/herself or with the help of the person of trust or the person who is responsible for helping and supporting victims.

If the applicant does not complete the request within seven days of being invited to do so, it will be assumed that s/he no longer wishes to submit the request.

If an applicant submits a complete request to the person for help and support, the person who receives the request is obliged to inform the dean within three days of receiving the request. Upon

³ This Rulebook is based on the Rulebook from the University of Belgrade, Faculty of Political Science from 2014 with almost no changes in content.

receiving this request, the dean shall determine and implement measures aimed at minimising contact between the applicant and the person named as perpetrator in the request until the procedure has been concluded.

Time frame: Within three days of receiving a proper request, the dean may appoint a person by decision or form a three-member commission to establish the facts of the incident.

The person providing the victim with assistance and support is not appointed to the commission. The commission must keep minutes and / or official notes. The commission is also responsible for interviewing everyone named in the proceedings and for gathering evidence in other ways.

The commission informs the dean of the faculty of its findings.

Outcome: The commission may establish that sexual harassment or blackmail occurred, that no sexual harassment or blackmail occurred, or that there is insufficient evidence to demonstrate that sexual harassment or blackmail occurred. The commission must inform the dean of its findings/ruling and must provide him/her with all the materials on the case within seven days of their decision.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Zorana Antonijević in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

